

MULTIPLE OBJECT RECOGNITION AND DEPTH ESTIMATION FROM STEREO IMAGES

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ABSTRACT - Recent advances in computer technology have enabled powerful hardware to be obtained at affordable costs. This way, the fields of applications that require high processing power such as image processing, artificial neural networks and deep learning have been increased. Some of these applications are autonomous vehicle navigation, robot guidance, object recognition, speech recognition, medical analysis, production quality control and safety systems.

The objective of this research was to develop a computer vision software to perform the calibration of a stereo camera system, to classify multiple objects in video frames using convolutional neural networks, to locate matching objects on image pairs, to calculate their distances to the stereo camera and to verify calculated values with measured values. Based on the results obtained, it has been concluded that proposed method can be adopted for industrial applications.

Keywords: Calibration, Convolutional neural network, Depth estimation, Image processing, Stereo vision

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1. INTRODUCTION

Considering the period of time starting from the industrial revolution to the present, it can be said that the great leap in the field of technology has begun with the invention of transistor in 1947, by William Shockley from Bell research laboratories. This unprecedented development paved the way for the pioneers of computer science such as Alan Turing and John von Neumann and enabled us to reach the technologies we have today.

In parallel to the developments in electronics industry, in 1956 a young mathematician from Dartmouth University, John McCarthy introduced the concept of a thinking machine and used the term artificial intelligence for the first time.

The first artificial intelligence approach that takes the human brain as a model was the design of a single layer neural network named **Perceptron**, proposed by Frank Rosenblatt in 1958. Inspired by the way neurons work together, Rosenblatt conceived Perceptron as a supervised learning algorithm for binary classification.

Figure 1. A photo of John McCarthy (Professor-John-McCarthy-shows-off-computer-chess)

Figure 2. A photo of Frank Rosenblatt
Eby, M. (2020)

In neuroscience, synaptic plasticity is defined as the brain's tendency to change the nature of connections between individual synapses in response to changing needs. A neuron produces an output signal (fires) if the sum of the signals it receives from neighboring neurons exceeds a certain threshold. Since neurons receive stronger or weaker signals depending on the nature of their synaptic connections, a neuron in the network performs a sort of weighted addition. Neuroscientists argue that learning is possible by this weighted transmission model where the weight changes over time. Rosenblatt's Perceptron approach is considered as the ancestor of deep learning, an important branch of today's artificial intelligence technology.

Fig 3. Biological and artificial neuron: a) Biological neuron b) Artificial neuron c) Detailed workings of a neuron (Samarasinghe, 2006)

During the period between 1960 and 2010 various neural network and machine learning concepts have been brought to light and starting from year 2010 onwards with the help of advances in computer hardware deep learning has been accepted as the most dominant artificial intelligence paradigm such that the term deep learning has become to mean artificial intelligence.

Figure 4. Difference between machine learning and deep learning (Wolfewicz, 2021)

In supervised deep learning, an accurate classification or prediction is possible with a large amount of labeled data fed into a multilayer artificial neural network without the need for specific feature extraction software. Feeding inputs, calculating outputs with the default weights, calculating errors using loss function, updating the weights by back-propagation constitute the basic stages of model training. This training process terminates when the errors converge to an acceptable value.

Figure 5. Multiple layer perceptron (Sonmez, 2018)

Back propagation takes place layer by layer backwards from the output layer. MSE (Mean squared error), which is a differentiable function, is mostly used as the loss function in order to obtain the error at output layer neurons.

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{total}} = \sum \frac{1}{2} (\text{desired} - \text{predicted})^2$$

The weight of a link is expressed by the product of the partial derivatives taken at all nodes (including neuron's own activation function) starting from output layer to the link itself according to chain rule. The learning coefficient is used to calculate the new value of the weight.

$$Wx_{\text{new}} = Wx_{\text{present}} - \eta \cdot \frac{d\mathcal{E}}{dW}$$

2. GENERAL INFORMATION

2.1. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN, ConvNet) is an artificial neural network algorithm that makes use of convolution operation for image classification in deep learning. It was developed by the French computer scientist Yann LeCun from year 1989 to 1998, and it has been widely adopted by the software community after 2010

Figure 6. A photo of Yann LeCun (Yann LeCun | Tandon School of Engineering)

The convolutional neural network model is quite similar to the ordinary neural network model. It consists of neurons whose weights and balances are trained. A neuron in the network multiplies values of all its upstream neurons by the weights of their connection, sums these values, and passes through its activation function in order to eliminate linearity. However, unlike classical artificial neural network, convolutional neural networks consist of two basic blocks; Convolutional block and fully connected block.

Figure 7. Convolutional neural network model. (Convolutional Neural Network)

Convolution block consists of convolutional layers and pooling layers in ordered pairs. This block is the part where feature extraction takes place. Whereas fully connected block is in classical neural network architecture, which consists of fully connected neurons. In this block, the classification takes place according to the convolution block outputs.

The advantage of CNN model is that it is much faster than the classical neural network. For example, an image of 3 channels 416x416 pixel size, the input layer in the classical artificial neural network model will consist of 519168 neurons. Since each of these neurons will be connected to hidden layer neurons, the size of the matrices holding the connection weights will dramatically increase the memory and processing power consumption. However in CNN model, the need for memory and processing power is reduced thousands of times by preserving the meaningful elements in the image and reducing the input size at every stage with the convolution and pooling operations applied consecutively. As for the weight update, elements trained by back propagation in the convolution block are convolution filters (kernel) themselves. Filters are generally preferred in 3x3 or 5x5 sizes.

Figure 8. Convolution operation (Reynolds, 2019)

The output of final pooling layer in convolution block is transformed into single dimension array (flattened) and fed to the fully connected block where the extracted features are mapped to the network outputs. The last fully connected layer consists of neurons holding probabilities of each class. For example, if an image is to be classified as piano, guitar or flute, there will be three neurons in the output layer. The output values of these three neurons, which symbolize the instruments, will be probabilities between 0 and 1. The neuron with the highest of these values determines the result of classification for the image being analyzed.

Basically, three different application approaches can be mentioned in image analysis with convolutional neural networks. In this study, Yolo v3 model is chosen for classification of images.

Image classification	Classification w. localization	Detection
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classifies a picture • Predicts probability of object 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detects an object in a picture • Predicts probability of object and where it is located 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detects up to several objects in a picture • Predicts probabilities of objects and where they are located
Traditional CNN	Simplified YOLO, R-CNN	YOLO, R-CNN

Fig 9. Types of object recognition algorithms (Amidi, Convolutional Neural Networks cheat sheet)

2.1.1. YOLO NEURAL NETWORK MODEL

YOLO (You only look once) is a very efficient real-time multi-object recognition algorithm that was publicly released in 2015 by Joseph Redmond et al. Unlike traditional CNN, it is based on finding five meaningful sub-regions by dividing the image into parts, instead of searching for regions that may be meaningful in the whole image. Thus, the amount of bounding boxes that can be extracted from an image reaches as high as 1805. The output data structure of a bounding box has the following elements ;

- Bounding box center (bx,by)
- Width of bounding box (bw)
- Height of bounding box (bh)
- Probability of an object found in box (pc)
- Array of class probabilities for each class id (c)

Figure 10. Yolo bounding box structure (Maj, 2018)

YOLO is simple by its design which allows classification of multiple objects simultaneously using a single convolution block.

YOLO is fast. The standard version can classify at 45fps with the Titan X GPU. The simplified version, on the other hand, reaches 150 fps, although its sensitivity is slightly reduced. (Redmon, 2016) Another trade-off for high speed is the loss of performance in recognizing small objects..

YOLO training and testing codes are open source. Moreover, pre-trained models including certain objects can be downloaded from the Internet.

Figure 11. Yolo convolutional network architecture (Redmon, 2016)

In YOLO, the input image is processed by dividing it into parts. Assuming that the image is divided into $S \times S$ cells, the predictions will be expressed as a tensor of size $S \times S \times (5B+C)$, where B is the quantity of bounding boxes and C is classification possibilities.

Figure 12. Bounding boxes and class probability map (Redmon, 2016)

2.2. IMAGE PROCESSING

Almost everyone working in the field of image processing needs the open source OpenCV library at some point. OpenCV is an image processing library developed by Intel in C and C++ languages, suitable for Linux, Windows and MacOS operating systems. When Intel research group officials were developing this library, they saw that different computer vision infrastructures were being created in computer science faculties of many respected universities. Since image processing consumes a lot of resources, they decided to distribute this library free of charge starting from 1999 instead of marketing it, anticipating that powerful processors will increase their sales. Their decision allowed millions of scientists and students to work on a common ground.

OpenCV is an extremely useful library containing thousands of functions that makes possible camera interface access, matrix operations, image viewing and manipulation, conversion between formats, sharpening, blurring, morphological operations, thresholding, various transformations (Canny, Laplace, Convolution, DFT, Histogram equalization) contour finding, contour matching, segmentation, motion tracking, camera calibration, machine learning, and deep learning. In this study OpenCV version 4 has been used for development.

2.2.1 STEREO CAMERA CALIBRATION AND RECTIFICATION

Camera, with its simplest definition, is a device that maps 3D world into 2D plane. Whereas a stereo camera is a set of two cameras mounted on the same fixture looking at a common scene as shown on Fig 12. The purpose of the stereo camera is to obtain the depth information of the objects in the scene

Figure 12. Stereo kamera arrangement (Santoro, 2012)

In order to obtain accurate dimensions from objects in the scene, translation and rotation relationship of cameras with respect to each other must be known exactly. Even high end commercial stereo camera models on the market may have some flaws. For instance, image pairs captured with the stereo camera that has been used for this research were subject to visible rotational mismatch both in pitch and yaw axis. Another problem is the distortion of the rays that pass through the lens and fall on the sensor depending on the manufacturing quality and focal length of the lens. These distortions also need to be corrected in software for a precise image analysis.

Figure 13. Radial distortions (Sadekar, 2020)

Figure 14. Tangential distortion (Steward, 2021)

Therefore, the most critical step in stereo image processing is individual and stereo calibration of the cameras. A calibration that is not done meticulously will undoubtedly lead to erroneous results.

Before detailing the calibration process, it would be useful to state some basics about the camera matrix. A camera matrix is a 3x4 matrix which describes the mapping from 3D points in the world to 2D points in an image as shown in figure 15.

$$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} p_1 & p_2 & p_3 & p_4 \\ p_5 & p_6 & p_7 & p_8 \\ p_9 & p_{10} & p_{11} & p_{12} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

homogeneous image
3 x 1
Camera matrix
3 x 4
homogeneous world point
4 x 1

Figure 15. Camera model camera and matrix (Kitani, Camera Matrix)

Camera matrix can be expressed as a combination of intrinsic and extrinsic parameters. Intrinsic parameters include camera's optical center, focal length, and lens distortion information. External parameters, on the other hand, contain information about the location and orientation of the camera, more specifically translation and rotation information with reference to the world coordinate system in which the camera resides.

A camera with known internal and external parameters means a camera whose calibration matrix is known. Images taken with that camera are corrected by the rectification process that requires calibration matrix. The figure 16 shows the rectification of the camera matrix with decomposed intrinsic and extrinsic parameters. Here P stands for rectified projection matrix, K intrinsic parameters, R and t rotation and translation parameters

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{K}[\mathbf{R}|\mathbf{t}]$$

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} f & 0 & p_x \\ 0 & f & p_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r_1 & r_2 & r_3 & | & t_1 \\ r_4 & r_5 & r_6 & | & t_2 \\ r_7 & r_8 & r_9 & | & t_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

intrinsic parameters
extrinsic parameters

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} r_1 & r_2 & r_3 \\ r_4 & r_5 & r_6 \\ r_7 & r_8 & r_9 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{t} = \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \\ t_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

3D rotation
3D translation

Figure 16. Projection matrix obtained from intrinsic and extrinsic parameters (Kitani, Camera Matrix)

In the intrinsic parameters, f indicates the focal length, p_x and p_y indicate pixel coordinates of camera optical center on the image. In the extrinsic parameters, the elements t_1, t_2, t_3 represent the translation of camera in x, y, z axes with reference to world space coordinate system. The elements r_1, r_2, \dots, r_9 defines rotation matrix that is used to perform a rotation in Euclidian space and which is the product of the rotation matrices of each axis. More clearly;

$$R = Z(\theta) \cdot X(\psi) \cdot Y(\varphi) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta & 0 \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \psi & -\sin \psi \\ 0 & \sin \psi & \cos \psi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \varphi & 0 & \sin \varphi \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \varphi & 0 & \cos \varphi \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 17. Rotation matrix (Abdelhamid, 2011)

In the light of above information, calibration process of a stereo camera using the OpenCV library has been conducted in following steps ;

- a) A chessboard image consisting of black and white squares of known sizes is printed out on a paper at 1:1 scale, and pasted on a rigid board in order to prevent it from bending.
- b) At least 12 photos, preferably more, are taken randomly while moving the board to different locations and rotations, in a way that all chessboard squares remain inside the frame of both cameras.
- c) From all images saved by left camera, intersection points of each black and white square are found using opencv's `findChessboardCorners` function, and these are added to a c vector.
- d) Camera matrix, distortion coefficients, rotation and translation matrices of the left camera are obtained by passing the vector populated above and the vector consisting of pixel coordinates of the corresponding points in the printed image as arguments to the `calibrateCamera` function of the opencv library, with the origin being the top left corner.
- e) From all images saved by right camera, intersection points of each black and white square are found using opencv's `findChessboardCorners` function, and these are added to a c vector.

f) Camera matrix, distortion coefficients, rotation and translation matrices of the right camera are obtained by passing the vector populated above and the vector consisting of pixel coordinates of the corresponding points in the printed image, as arguments to the `calibrateCamera` function of the `opencv` library, with the origin being the top left corner.

g) Matrices and parameters obtained from `calibrateCamera` function are passed to `stereoCalibrate` function which outputs the transform between left and right camera ; rotation matrix and translation vector. This function also returns fundamental matrix for uncalibrated cameras and essential matrix for calibrated cameras which are used to compute a corresponding point in right image from a given point in left image, and vice versa.

h) Finally, by passing the matrices obtained by the `stereoCalibrate` function to the `stereoRectify` function as parameters, R_1 and R_2 matrices (rectification matrices) are obtained, which will ensure that the objects are at the same line on the vertical axis in the images taken with the stereo camera.

j) All matrices obtained from `stereoCalibrate` and `stereoRectify` functions are saved.

After this stage, for each captured image pair by the stereo camera within the application, `initUndistortRectifyMap` and `remap` functions are called in order to get corrected image.

2.2.2. DEPTH ESTIMATION FROM STEREO IMAGES

Once camera setup is neatly calibrated and captured images are undistorted and remapped as explained in section 2.2.1, depth values of scene objects can be extracted using basic triangulation as long as camera positions and orientations remain unchanged. Figure 18 shows basic projection geometry in stereo imaging.

Figure 18. Stereo imaging projection geometry (Ortiz, 2018)

According to this representation, Z is the depth value of the object to calculate, B is the distance between cameras, f is the focal length, CxL , CyL , CxR , CyR are the pixel coordinates of object center point in the right and left image planes. The distance (B) between the cameras is given in camera technical specification. The focal length (f) is the lens focal length scaled with image size to sensor size ratio, and it is available in internal parameters obtained as a result of the calibration. The pixel coordinates of the object centers in the image plane are available in the bounding box structure estimated by the Yolo convolutional neural network model.

The top view of Figure 18 is shown in Figure 19 ;

Figure 19. Top view of stereo imaging projection geometry

Following equality is inferred from similar triangles ;

$$\frac{CxL}{f} = \frac{X + \frac{B}{2}}{Z} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{CxR}{f} = \frac{X - \frac{B}{2}}{Z}$$

From above equality, depth of an object Z is defined in terms of disparity ($CxL - CxR$).

$$Z = \frac{B \cdot f}{CxL - CxR}$$

2.2.3. INTEGRATION OF IMAGE PROCESSING AND NEURAL NETWORK

The OpenCV library comes with deep learning module from version 3.3 onwards. Thanks to this module, the integration of different pre-trained artificial neural network modules into user software is carried out without the need for another library. In this project, weight and configuration files of the YoloV3 neural network model was run through this module..

Loading the neural network model is made with readNet function under the cv::dnn namespace. This function takes the path to the weight file (.weights) and the path to the model's configuration file (.cfg) as argument.

The YoloV3 pre-trained set is designed to recognize 80 classes. These classes are from 1 to 80 respectively in the output layer; human, bicycle, car, motorcycle, airplane, bus, train, truck, boat, traffic light, fire hydrant, stop sign, parking meter, bench, bird, cat, dog, horse, sheep, cow, elephant, bear, zebra, giraffe , backpack, umbrella, handbag, tie, suitcase, frisbee, skis, snowboard, ball, kite, baseball bat, baseball glove, skateboard, surfboard, tennis racket, bottle, wine glass, mug, fork, knife, spoon, bowl, banana, apple, sandwich, orange, broccoli, carrot, sausage, pizza, donut, cake, chair, armchair, flower pot, bed, dining table, closet, television, laptop, computer mouse, remote control, keyboard, pocket phone, microwave oven, oven, toaster, sink, refrigerator, book, clock, vase, scissors, teddy bear, hair dryer and toothbrush.

Following steps have been taken in order to classify objects with OpenCV dnn module and pre-trained neural network model ;

a) The path to Yolo weights and configuration files downloaded from Yolo website are passed to readNet function which returns an object of type cv::dnn::Net

b) The artificial neural network infrastructure is set to OpenCV by calling the setPreferableBackend(DNN_BACKEND_OPENCV) method with returned Net variable

c) Calling the setPreferableTarget(DNN_TARGET_CPU) method with the same Net variable, for CPU (or GPU) based operation is set.

d) An array of strings to hold class names is created and filled in the same order as neural network output neurons. For this research coco.names text file is downloaded from Yolo website and used.

e) Whenever a new image is captured, it is corrected according to the calibration matrix. (as explained in the calibration section 2.2.1)

f) Rectified image is converted to 4 dimension tensor (NCHW) using dnn::blobfromImage function

g) setInput function is called with Net variable and blob variable is passed as argument.

- h) A vector of type cv::Mat is created to hold detected bounding boxes, classes, and confidence
- i) Forward method is called with Net variable and cv::Mat vector and getUnconnectedOutLayerNames(Net variable) are passed as argument.
- j) cv::Mat vector is filled with detected bounding boxes, classes and confidences by the return of forward method.
- k) cv::Mat vector is parsed and all necessary information are extracted.

3. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Within the scope of this work, a native compiled linux application is developed using C++ language. The graphical user interface is made with Qt library. The images captured from stereo camera were processed with OpenCV library and its deep neural network module. Detected objects and their distances to the stereo camera are reported on a datagrid.

3.1. EQUIPMENT

Following equipment is used for the application ;

- 1x Nvidia Jetson Nano AI computer
- 1x Sony IM219-83 based Stereo camera
- 2x CSI interface cable
- 1x Tripod
- 1 x Mounting plate

3.1.1. Nvidia Jetson Nano Computer

- GPU 128-core Maxwell
- CPU 4-core ARM A57 @ 1.43 GHz
- Operating system Linux
- RAM 4 GB 64 Bit LPDDR4 | 25.6 GB/s
- Video Encode 4K @ 30 | 4x 1080p @ 30 | 9x 720p @ 30 (H.264/H.265)
- Video Decode 4K @ 60 | 2x 4K @ 30 | 8x 1080p @ 30 | 18x 720p @ 30 (H.264/H.265)
- Camera 2x MIPI CSI-2 DPHY lanes
- Gigabit Ethernet, M.2 Key E
- USB 4x USB 3.0, USB 2.0 Micro-B
- Other GPIO, I2C, I2S, SPI, UART
- Dimensions 100 mm x 80 mm x 29 mm

Figure 20. Jetson Nano Computer

3.1.2. Sony IM219-83 based stereo kamera

Figure 21. Stereo Camera

Sensor: Sony IMX219

Resolution: 3280×2464 (per camera)

Lens specifications:

CMOS size: 1/4inch

Focal Length: 2.6mm

Angle of View: 83/73/50 degree (diagonal/horizontal/vertical)

Distortion: <1%

Baseline Length: 60mm

ICM20948:

Accelerometer:

Resolution: 16-bit

Measuring Range (configurable): $\pm 2, \pm 4, \pm 8, \pm 16g$

Operating Current: 68.9uA

Gyroscope:

Resolution: 16-bit

Measuring Range (configurable): $\pm 250, \pm 500, \pm 1000, \pm 2000^\circ/\text{sec}$

Operating Current: 1.23mA

Magnetometer:

Resolution: 16-bit

Measuring Range: $\pm 4900\mu T$

Operating Current: 90uA

Dimension: 24mm \times 85mm

3.1.3. CSI Camera interface cable

Figure 22. Stereo Camera CSI interface cable

3.1.4. Tripod and mounting plate

Figure 23. Tripod and mounting plate

3.1.5. Experimental environment

Figure 24. Experimental environment

Figure 25. A scene from experiment

3.2. METHOD

The flowchart of the software is as shown in figure 26.

Figure 26. Software flow diagram

4. RESULTS

4.1. CALIBRATION RESULTS

Calibration menu implemented in the application provides complete calibration workflow as well as saving and retrieving calibration data for later use. Images in figure 28 are taken using using the application ;

Figure 27. Calibration menu

Figure 28. Images taken for calibration

Corners of checkerboard images are detected correctly as shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Detected corners during calibration

The matrices obtained as a result of the calibration process are shown below ;

LEFT CAMERA - CAMERA AND DISTORTION MATRICES

K: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

data: [5.8166088991359027e+02, 0., 3.3570997024361776e+02, 0.,
7.7387600203886643e+02, 2.8015027751270867e+02, 0., 0., 1.]

D: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 1 cols: 5 dt: d

data: [-1.6160937401860759e-01, 9.0319323291590248e-01,
-1.3781131824954437e-03, -4.5921517824351485e-04,
-1.9278208853746575e+00]

board_width: 9

board_height: 6

square_size: 2.

RIGHT CAMERA -CAMERA AND DISTORSION MATRICES

K: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6544603

data: [5.8249657630589957e+02, 0., 3.3435659791968590e+02, 0.,
7.7591331524355746e+02, 2.4632547239438091e+02, 0., 0., 1.]

D: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 1 cols: 5 dt: d

data: [-1.4842077372742965e-01, 6.4051178026583100e-01,
1.4737778247401337e-04, -9.1167971051625096e-04,
-9.5386051458102916e-01]

board_width: 9

board_height: 6

square_size: 2.

STEREO CALIBRATION , K1, K2, D1, D2, R, T , E , F, R1, R2, P1, P2, Q MATRICES

K1: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

data: [5.8166088991359027e+02, 0., 3.3570997024361776e+02, 0.,
7.7387600203886643e+02, 2.8015027751270867e+02, 0., 0., 1.]

K2: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

data: [5.8249657630589957e+02, 0., 3.3435659791968590e+02, 0.,
7.7591331524355746e+02, 2.4632547239438091e+02, 0., 0., 1.]

D1: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 1 cols: 5 dt: d

data: [-1.6160937401860759e-01, 9.0319323291590248e-01,
-1.3781131824954437e-03, -4.5921517824351485e-04,
-1.9278208853746575e+00]

D2: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 1 cols: 5 dt: d

data: [-1.4842077372742965e-01, 6.4051178026583100e-01,
1.4737778247401337e-04, -9.1167971051625096e-04,
-9.5386051458102916e-01]

R: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

data: [9.9992804293714921e-01, -2.4373835298358540e-03,
-1.1745982692441316e-02, 2.4212550560881551e-03,
9.9999610668890793e-01, -1.3871304840331348e-03,
1.1749317930672128e-02, 1.3585906502149082e-03,
9.9993005143340352e-01]

T: [-6.0163964562455252e+00, -1.3622847988624018e-02,
-1.0461782337464186e-01]

E: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

data: [9.3247261663228259e-05, 1.0459890819100304e-01,
-1.3767013661910412e-02, -3.3921740621952183e-02,
8.4288137330619066e-03, 6.0172044570800143e+00,
-9.4536261062024300e-04, -6.0164062366477848e+00,
8.1855131917909548e-03]

F: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

data: [9.1465732738861130e-10, 7.7116616449344381e-07,
-2.9489689694408959e-04, -2.4979321189411534e-07,

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6544603

4.6651696740234350e-08, 2.5843916854448444e-02,
5.5823112325540603e-05, -2.6106886873434109e-02, 1.]

R1: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

data: [9.9998409756045259e-01, -1.4945817662057851e-04,
5.6375782443052764e-03, 1.5334986050427035e-04,
9.999975027098931e-01, -6.8988533769186189e-04,
-5.6374737274337934e-03, 6.9073888866935033e-04,
9.9998387075480388e-01]

R2: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 3 dt: d

data: [9.9984628703230816e-01, 2.2639389008504455e-03,
1.7386111939144289e-02, -2.2759407140120580e-03,
9.9999718522097703e-01, 6.7055498599785006e-04,
-1.7384544905563154e-02, -7.1002167302160191e-04,
9.9984862527667173e-01]

P1: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 4 dt: d

data: [7.7489465864121189e+02, 0., 3.2709444046020508e+02, 0., 0.,
7.7489465864121189e+02, 2.6338606071472168e+02, 0., 0., 0., 1.,
0.]

P2: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 3 cols: 4 dt: d

data: [7.7489465864121189e+02, 0., 3.2709444046020508e+02,
-4.6627902095334048e+03, 0., 7.7489465864121189e+02,
2.6338606071472168e+02, 0., 0., 0., 1., 0.]

Q: !!opencv-matrix

rows: 4 cols: 4 dt: d

data: [1., 0., 0., -3.2709444046020508e+02, 0., 1., 0.,
-2.6338606071472168e+02, 0., 0., 0., 7.7489465864121189e+02, 0.,
0., 1.6618690179474188e-01, 0.]

4.2. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Wall clock, computer keyboard, tennis racket and bottle were used as objects to be detected in the experiments. Image capture was performed live in video format. While recording the measurements, the clock and computer keyboard were moved from near to far, the soda bottle from far to near, and the tennis racket was moved back and forth by small distances. Screenshots of the application showing measurement records are as follows.

Table 1. Measurements taken while wall clock moves away from camera

Stereo vision based object detection and depth O.Unsalver 2022

LEFT CAMERA

RIGHT CAMERA

Results

	Detected object type	Confidence (%)	Position on left camera (px)	Position	Disparity (px)	Depth (mm)
1	Clock	34.1366%	351	264	85.6466	407.484
2	Clock	58.9998%	351	270	79.6466	438.181
3	Clock	71.2586%	349	279	68.6466	508.396
4	Clock	93.7128%	346	283	61.6466	566.124
5	Clock	85.6672%	342	285	55.6466	627.166
6	Clock	88.9715%	339	288	49.6466	702.961
7	Clock	89.2698%	339	293	44.6466	781.686
8	Clock	48.1148%	350	311	37.6466	927.033
9	Clock	42.5903%	358	323	33.6466	1037.24

Add detected objects to list

Calibration settings

Stereo calibration data successfully loaded...
 Focal lengths with reference to projected image
 Left camera 581.661
 Right camera 582.497
 Principal points offset with reference to projected image
 Left camera 335.71
 Right camera 334.357 >>

Table 2. Measurements taken while keyboard moves away from stereo camera

Stereo vision based object detection and depth O.Unsalver 2022

LEFT CAMERA

RIGHT CAMERA

Results

	Detected object type	Confidence (%)	Position on left camera (px)	Position	Disparity (px)	Depth (mm)
1	Keyboard	31.6519%	372	279	91.6466	380.807
2	Keyboard	32.6462%	367	291	74.6466	467.532
3	Keyboard	74.5879%	374	282	90.6466	385.008
4	Keyboard	66.6821%	379	290	87.6466	398.186
5	Keyboard	29.5655%	391	321	68.6466	508.396
6	Keyboard	55.4571%	392	328	62.6466	557.088
7	Keyboard	43.2092%	397	338	57.6466	605.407
8	Keyboard	27.6697%	394	340	52.6466	662.904
9						

Add detected objects to list

Calibration settings

Stereo calibration data successfully loaded...
 Focal lengths with reference to projected image
 Left camera 581.661
 Right camera 582.497
 Principal points offset with reference to projected image
 Left camera 335.71
 Right camera 334.357 >>

Table 3. Measurements taken while bottle moves towards stereo camera

ereo vision based object detection and depth
O.Unsalver 202

LEFT CAMERA

RIGHT CAMERA

Results

	Detected object type	Confidence (%)	Position on left camera (px)	Positiolr	Disparity (px)	Depth (mm)
1	Toothbrush	22.0674%	357	333	22.6466	1541.05
2	Bottle	22.8446%	363	340	21.6466	1612.24
3	Bottle	32.3897%	358	332	24.6466	1416
4	Vase	27.4716%	347	317	28.6466	1218.28
5	Bottle	60.798%	336	303	31.6466	1102.79
6	Vase	39.4818%	329	291	36.6466	952.329
7	Vase	37.8121%	325	282	41.6466	837.995
8	Vase	38.5117%	293	243	48.6466	717.412
9	Vase	22.6508%	277	219	56.6466	616.094

Add detected objects to list

Calibration settings

Stereo calibration data succesfully loaded...
 Focal leghts with reference to projected image
 Left camera 581.661
 Right camera 582.497
 Principal points offset with reference to projected image
 Left camera 335.71
 Right camera 334.357

>>

During the experiment, bottle was classified as vase many times. However because bounding boxes were correctly located, classification errors did not affect the measurement values.

Table 4. Measurements taken while tennis racket moves back and forth

ereo vision based object detection and depth
O.Unsalver 202

LEFT CAMERA

RIGHT CAMERA

Results

	Detected object type	Confidence (%)	Position on left camera (px)	Positiolr	Disparity (px)	Depth (mm)
1	Tennis racket	49.9059%	469	431	36.6466	952.329
2	Tennis racket	42.521%	471	432	37.6466	927.033
3	Tennis racket	42.6631%	470	429	39.6466	880.268
4	Tennis racket	70.761%	464	431	31.6466	1102.79
5	Tennis racket	80.1249%	436	399	35.6466	979.045
6	Tennis racket	63.2886%	456	420	34.6466	1007.3
7	Tennis racket	88.0065%	432	402	28.6466	1218.28
8	Tennis racket	79.3431%	409	380	27.6466	1262.35
9	Tennis racket	20.3401%	430	401	27.6466	1262.35

Add detected objects to list

Calibration settings

Stereo calibration data succesfully loaded...
 Focal leghts with reference to projected image
 Left camera 581.661
 Right camera 582.497
 Principal points offset with reference to projected image
 Left camera 335.71
 Right camera 334.357

>>

In order to evaluate measurement accuracy, another experiment was performed by keeping the wall clock and tennis racket fixed. On this scene, the actual distance from wall clock to the camera was 600mm, and from the tennis racket to camera was 1200mm.

Table 5. Measurements taken when tennis racket and wall clock stay steady

ereo vision based object detection and depth
O.Unsalver 2022

LEFT CAMERA

RIGHT CAMERA

Results

	Detected object type	Confidence (%)	Position on left camera (px)	Positior	Disparity (px)	Depth (mm)
1	Clock	65.0964%	268	210	56.6466	616.094
2	Tennis racket	26.4247%	478	447	29.6466	1177.19
3	Person	36.6376%	161	136	23.6466	1475.88
4	Clock	65.8477%	268	210	56.6466	616.094
5	Tennis racket	25.4803%	480	449	29.6466	1177.19
6	Person	33.6022%	161	135	24.6466	1416
7	Clock	65.1824%	269	211	56.6466	616.094
8	Tennis racket	23.7386%	480	449	29.6466	1177.19
9	Person	28.7963%	161	137	22.6466	1541.05

Add detected objects to list

Calibration settings

to projected image
 Left camera 335.71
 Right camera 334.357
 Stereo calibration data succesfully loaded..

Focal leights with reference to projected image
 Left camera 581.661
 Right camera 582.497
 Principal points offset with reference to projected Image
 Left camera 335.71
 Right camera 334.357

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this project titled "Multiple Object Recognition and Depth Estimation from Stereo Images", the aim was to recognize multiple objects on the scene using a pre-trained convolutional neural network model and to calculate perpendicular distances of these objects to the stereo camera setup. The steps taken in the software are summarized as recognizing objects in the image of one of the cameras using convolutional neural network model, finding the same contents inside their bounding boxes in the other camera's image by template matching method, and calculating the depth using the disparity information.

In the experiments carried out without calibration, it was observed that objects in the right and left images were at different levels on the vertical axis and they were slightly rotated relative to each other. This error is thought to be caused by some minor differences between cameras in terms of geometrical relationship between the lens and the sensor or by the sensors not being mounted perfectly on the PCB. Looking at screenshots in the measurement findings section, black bands with inclined inward edges are noticed at the bottom of the left image and at the top of the right image. Based on this observation, it is understood as a result of calibration process that left image has been shifted up, right image has been shifted down, and the horizon lines have been equalized by rotating two images in the opposite direction with respect to each other. As a result, it is possible to say that the calibration process was successful.

In the experiments during which the objects were moved, depth value changed in parallel with the direction of the movement. Measurement errors while objects were stationary, were below $\pm 4\%$. At the time this research was completed the opencv library pre-installed on Nvidia Jetson Nano was not compiled with GPU support, therefore neural network had to be run with CPU support. Yet 2.5fps frame rate was achieved in the program cycle consisting of image capture from two cameras in live video mode, image rectification, classification with Yolo neural network, image matching and user interface update.

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APPENDIX

Appx 1. Source code for calibration

```

#include <opencv2/core.hpp>
#include <opencv2/calib3d.hpp>
#include <opencv2/highgui.hpp>
#include <opencv2/imgproc.hpp>
#include <stdio.h>
#include <iostream>
#include <QDebug>
#include <sys/stat.h>
using namespace std;
using namespace cv;

//CAMERA CALIBRATION VARIABLES
int board_width, board_height, num_imgs;
float square_size;
char* left_imgs_directory;
char* right_imgs_directory;
char* imgs_filename;
char* out_file_left;
char* out_file_right;
char* extension;
vector<vector<Point3f>> object_points;
vector<vector<Point2f>> imagePoints1, imagePoints2;
vector<Point2f> corners1, corners2;
vector<vector<Point2f>> left_img_points, right_img_points;
Mat img1, img2, gray1, gray2;

//RECTIFICATION & STEREO MAPPING VARIABLES
Mat R1, R2, P1, P2, Q;
Mat K1, K2, R;
Vec3d T;
Mat D1, D2;
Mat lmapx, lmapy, rmapx, rmapy;

double xfocalLength_Left=0;
double xfocalLength_Right=0;
double xprincipalPoint_Left=0;
double xprincipalPoint_Right=0;
bool calibrationCompleted=false;

double computeReprojectionErrors(const vector< vector< Point3f > >& objectPoints,
                                const vector< vector< Point2f > >& imagePoints,
                                const vector< Mat >& rvecs, const vector< Mat >& tvecs,
                                const Mat& cameraMatrix , const Mat& distCoeffs) {
    vector< Point2f > imagePointsX;

```

```

int i, totalPoints = 0;
double totalErr = 0, err;
vector< float > perViewErrors;
perViewErrors.resize(objectPoints.size());

for (i = 0; i < (int)objectPoints.size(); ++i) {
    projectPoints(Mat(objectPoints[i]), rvecs[i], tvecs[i], cameraMatrix,
                    distCoeffs, imagePointsX);
    err = norm(Mat(imagePoints[i]), Mat(imagePointsX), cv::NORM_L2);
    int n = (int)objectPoints[i].size();
    perViewErrors[i] = (float) std::sqrt(err*err/n);
    totalErr += err*err;
    totalPoints += n;
}
return std::sqrt(totalErr/totalPoints);
}

void load_image_points(int board_width, int board_height, int num_imgs, float square_size,
                      char* leftimg_dir, char* rightimg_dir, char* leftimg_filename, char* rightimg_filename, char* extension) {

    Size board_size = Size(board_width, board_height);

    for (int i = 1; i <= num_imgs; i++) {
        char left_img[100], right_img[100];
        sprintf(left_img, "%s%s%d.%s", leftimg_dir, leftimg_filename, i, extension);
        sprintf(right_img, "%s%s%d.%s", rightimg_dir, rightimg_filename, i, extension);
        img1 = imread(left_img, IMREAD_COLOR);
        img2 = imread(right_img, IMREAD_COLOR);
        cvtColor(img1, gray1, COLOR_BGR2GRAY);
        cvtColor(img2, gray2, COLOR_BGR2GRAY);

        bool found1 = false, found2 = false;

        found1 = cv::findChessboardCorners(img1, board_size, corners1, CALIB_CB_ADAPTIVE_THRESH | CALIB_CB_FILTER_QUADS);
        found2 = cv::findChessboardCorners(img2, board_size, corners2, CALIB_CB_ADAPTIVE_THRESH | CALIB_CB_FILTER_QUADS);

        if(!found1 || !found2){
            cout << "Chessboard find error!" << endl;
            cout << "leftImg: " << left_img << " and rightImg: " << right_img << endl;
            continue;
        }

        if (found1)
        {
            cornerSubPix(gray1, corners1, cv::Size(5, 5), cv::Size(-1, -1), TermCriteria(TermCriteria::EPS | TermCriteria::MAX_ITER , 30, 0.1));
            cv::drawChessboardCorners(gray1, board_size, corners1, found1);
        }
        if (found2)
        {

```

```

    cornerSubPix(gray2, corners2, cv::Size(5, 5), cv::Size(-1, -1), TermCriteria(TermCriteria::EPS | TermCriteria::MAX_ITER, 30, 0.1));
    cv::drawChessboardCorners(gray2, board_size, corners2, found2);
}
vector< Point3f > obj;
for (int i = 0; i < board_height; i++)
    for (int j = 0; j < board_width; j++)
        obj.push_back(Point3f((float)j * square_size, (float)i * square_size, 0));

if (found1 && found2) {
    cout << i << ". Found corners!" << endl;
    imagePoints1.push_back(corners1);
    imagePoints2.push_back(corners2);
    object_points.push_back(obj);
}
}
for (int i = 0; i < imagePoints1.size(); i++) {
    vector< Point2f > v1, v2;
    for (int j = 0; j < imagePoints1[i].size(); j++) {
        v1.push_back(Point2f((double)imagePoints1[i][j].x, (double)imagePoints1[i][j].y));
        v2.push_back(Point2f((double)imagePoints2[i][j].x, (double)imagePoints2[i][j].y));
    }
    left_img_points.push_back(v1);
    right_img_points.push_back(v2);
}
}

int calibrate(char* leftcalib_file, char* rightcalib_file, char* leftimg_dir, char* rightimg_dir, char* leftimg_filename, char* rightimg_filename, char*
extension, char* outfile_stereo, int num_imgs)
{
    board_width=9;
    board_height=6;
    square_size=2.0f;
    load_image_points(board_width, board_height, num_imgs, square_size,
        leftimg_dir, rightimg_dir, leftimg_filename, rightimg_filename, extension);

    qDebug()<< "Left Camera individual calibration";

    Mat K1, K2;
    Mat D1, D2;
    vector<Mat> rvecs1, tvecs1, rvecs2, tvecs2;
    int flag = 0;
    flag |= CALIB_FIX_K4;
    flag |= CALIB_FIX_K5;

    calibrateCamera(object_points, imagePoints1, img1.size(), K1, D1, rvecs1, tvecs1, flag);
    calibrateCamera(object_points, imagePoints2, img2.size(), K2, D2, rvecs2, tvecs2, flag);

    qDebug() << "Calibration error Left: " << computeReprojectionErrors(object_points, imagePoints1, rvecs1, tvecs1, K1, D1) << endl;
    qDebug() << "Calibration error Right: " << computeReprojectionErrors(object_points, imagePoints2, rvecs2, tvecs2, K2, D2) << endl;
}

```

```
FileStorage fs1(leftcalib_file, FileStorage::WRITE);
fs1 << "K" << K1;
fs1 << "D" << D1;
fs1 << "board_width" << board_width;
fs1 << "board_height" << board_height;
fs1 << "square_size" << square_size;
printf("Done Calibration\n");

FileStorage fs2(rightcalib_file, FileStorage::WRITE);
fs2 << "K" << K2;
fs2 << "D" << D2;
fs2 << "board_width" << board_width;
fs2 << "board_height" << board_height;
fs2 << "square_size" << square_size;
printf("Done single camera Calibration\n");

printf("Starting stereo calibration\n");
Mat R,F,E;
Vec3d T;
flag = 0;
flag |= CALIB_FIX_INTRINSIC;

stereoCalibrate(object_points, left_img_points, right_img_points, K1, D1, K2, D2, img1.size(), R, T, E, F);

cv::FileStorage fss(outfile_stereo, cv::FileStorage::WRITE);
fss << "K1" << K1;
fss << "K2" << K2;
fss << "D1" << D1;
fss << "D2" << D2;
fss << "R" << R;
fss << "T" << T;
fss << "E" << E;
fss << "F" << F;

printf("Done Calibration\n");
printf("Starting Rectification\n");

cv::Mat R1, R2, P1, P2, Q;
stereoRectify(K1, D1, K2, D2, img1.size(), R, T, R1, R2, P1, P2, Q);

fss << "R1" << R1;
fss << "R2" << R2;
fss << "P1" << P1;
fss << "P2" << P2;
fss << "Q" << Q;

xfocalLength_Left= K1.at<double>(0,0);
xfocalLength_Right= K2.at<double>(0,0);
```

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6544603

```
xprincipalPoint_Left=K1.at<double>(0,2);
xprincipalPoint_Right=K2.at<double>(0,2);
calibrationCompleted=true;

printf("Done Rectification\n");

return 0;
}

void doNothing() { }

void GetRectifiedImages(Mat& inputLeft,Mat& inputRight,Mat& outputLeft,Mat& outputRight)
{
    initUndistortRectifyMap(K1, D1, R1, P1, inputLeft.size(), CV_32F, lmapx, lmapy);
    initUndistortRectifyMap(K2, D2, R2, P2, inputRight.size(), CV_32F, rmapx, rmapy);
    remap(inputLeft, outputLeft, lmapx, lmapy, cv::INTER_LINEAR);
    remap(inputRight,outputRight, rmapx, rmapy, cv::INTER_LINEAR);
}

void LoadCalibSettings(char* infile_stereo)
{
    cv::FileStorage fs1(infile_stereo, cv::FileStorage::READ);
    fs1["K1"] >> K1;
    fs1["K2"] >> K2;
    fs1["D1"] >> D1;
    fs1["D2"] >> D2;
    fs1["R"] >> R;
    fs1["T"] >> T;

    fs1["R1"] >> R1;
    fs1["R2"] >> R2;
    fs1["P1"] >> P1;
    fs1["P2"] >> P2;
    fs1["Q"] >> Q;

    xfocalLength_Left= K1.at<double>(0,0);
    xfocalLength_Right= K2.at<double>(0,0);
    xprincipalPoint_Left=K1.at<double>(0,2);
    xprincipalPoint_Right=K2.at<double>(0,2);

    calibrationCompleted=true;

    qDebug() << xfocalLength_Left << " " << xprincipalPoint_Left;
    qDebug() << xfocalLength_Right << " " << xprincipalPoint_Right;
}
```

Appx 2. Main loop source code (Object recognition on left image, template matching in right image, depth calculation)

```

void MainWindow::on_single_shot_requested()
{
    //SetCameraEnvironment();

    if(capLeft.read(leftImage) && capRight.read(rightImage))
    {
        if (calibrationCompleted) GetRectifiedImages(leftImage,rightImage,leftImage,rightImage);

        cv::Mat blob;
        cv::dnn::blobFromImage(leftImage,blob,OneDiv255,cv::Size(320,320),cv::Scalar(),true,false); //(416,416)
        network.setInput(blob);
        std::vector<cv::Mat> outs;

        network.forward(outs,network.getUnconnectedOutLayersNames());

        std::vector<int> classIds;
        std::vector<float> confidences;
        std::vector<cv::Rect> boxes;
        std::vector<int> centersX; //for suppression of multiple detections of same object

        for (size_t i=0; i<outs.size();i++)
        {
            float* data=(float*)outs[i].data;
            for (int j=0;j<outs[i].rows;j++ , data+=outs[i].cols)
            {
                cv::Mat scores=outs[i].row(j).colRange(5,outs[i].cols);
                cv::Point classIdPoint;
                double confidence;
                cv::minMaxLoc(scores,0,&confidence,0,&classIdPoint);

                if(confidence>0.2)
                {
                    qDebug()<< confidence << classIdPoint.x << classes[classIdPoint.x].data();
                    int centerX = (int)(data[0] * leftImage.cols);
                    int centerY = (int)(data[1] * leftImage.rows);
                    int width = (int)(data[2] * leftImage.cols);
                    int height = (int)(data[3] * leftImage.rows);
                    int left = centerX - (width / 2);
                    int top = centerY - (height / 2);

                    left= left>=0 ? left : 0;
                    top= top>=0 ? top : 0;
                    width= (left+width<=leftImage.cols) ? width : leftImage.cols-left;
                    height= (top+height<=leftImage.rows) ? height : leftImage.rows-top;
                }
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

for(auto x : centersX)
{
    float k=(float)centerX/(float)x;

    if (k>=0.95f && k<=1.05f) goto X001;
}
centersX.push_back(centerX);
qDebug() << data[2] << "x" << data[3];
qDebug() << "left=" << left << " top=" << top << " width=" << width << " height=" << height << " " << left+width << "x" << top+height << "
centerx=" << centerX << " centery=" << centerY;
qDebug() << leftImage.cols << "x" << leftImage.rows;

Rect region(left,top,width,height);

Mat cropped=leftImage(region);
Mat outputMatch;
double minVal,maxVal;
Point minLoc,maxLoc;

matchTemplate(rightImage,cropped,outputMatch,TM_CCORR_NORMED);
normalize(outputMatch, outputMatch,0,1,NORM_MINMAX,-1,Mat());
minMaxLoc(outputMatch,&minVal,&maxVal,&minLoc,&maxLoc,Mat());

rectangle(rightImage,maxLoc,Point(maxLoc.x+width,maxLoc.y+height),cv::Scalar(0,255,0),2,8,0);
int centerX2=maxLoc.x+width/2;

classIds.push_back(classIdPoint.x);
confidences.push_back((float)confidence);
boxes.push_back(cv::Rect(left, top, width, height));
cv::rectangle(leftImage, cv::Rect(left, top, width, height), cv::Scalar(0, 255, 0), 2, 8, 0);

double disparity=0;
double depth=0;

if (ui->checkBox->checkState())
{
    currentData=classes[classIdPoint.x].data();
    currentData[0]=currentData[0].toUpper();
    tableModel->setData(tableModel->index(currentRow,0),currentData);

    currentData=QString::number(100*confidence) + "%";
    tableModel->setData(tableModel->index(currentRow,1),currentData);

    tableModel->setData(tableModel->index(currentRow,2),QString::number(centerX));
    tableModel->setData(tableModel->index(currentRow,3),QString::number(centerX2));

    disparity=(centerX-xprincipalPoint_Left)-(centerX2-xprincipalPoint_Right);
    tableModel->setData(tableModel->index(currentRow,4),QString::number(disparity));

```

```
depth= xfocalLength_Left*60/disparity;
tableModel->setData(tableModel->index(currentRow,5),QString::number(depth));

currentRow++;
}

QPixmap mapLeft=MatToPixmap(leftImage);
ui->label_6->setPixmap(mapLeft);
QPixmap mapRight=MatToPixmap(rightImage);
ui->label_7->setPixmap(mapRight);
QApplication::processEvents();

}
X001:
doNothing();
}
}
}
```